

THE DISCOVERING OF CHITIN, ITS DERIVATIVES AND THEIR CHEMICAL PROPERTIES**Klishanets Alena,***Assistant Professor, Ph.D.***Stempen Igor,***Senior Lecturer**Yanka Kupala State University of Grodno
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Gagarina str., 18/2; 230011, Grodno, Belarus***Abstract**

Nowadays, the biopolymer chitin and its derivatives have been of certain scientific interests. Due to unique properties such as biocompatibility, biodegradability, nontoxicity, they have been applied in different fields: medicine, ecology, food industry and agriculture. All over the world, the shell of commercial crustaceans, the squid's gladius, the cuttlebone of cuttlefish, the silkworm pupa, the cockroaches, the biomass of microorganisms, diatoms, and bee-pods can serve to isolate chitin and its derivatives (chitosan, chitin-glucan complex) on the production scale. But, it has been established that the use of crustaceans as a source of chitin is very costly. At present, a negative factor is the contamination of the shells with heavy metals and other toxic waste products, which tends to increase. One of the sources of chitin and its derivatives can be the waste products of microbiological industry, in particular, *Aspergillus niger* L-4 biomass, a by-product of citric acid production. According to various sources, the cell wall of *Aspergillus niger* L-4 biomass may contain up to 30% of chitin, strongly bound to β -glucan and melanin in the chitin-glucan complex. The presence of β -glucan changes the properties of this biopolymer compared to native chitin and gives the valuable opportunities for application of chitin-glucan complex. Thus, the isolation of the chitin-glucan complex from the raw mycelium of the fungus *Aspergillus niger* requires low costs and at the same time solves a number of problems associated with the processing of the by-product. A very urgent task for the Republic of Belarus is to develop a technology for isolating the chitin-glucan complex from domestic raw materials, namely from the by-product of citric acid production.

Keywords: chitin, chitosan, chitin-glucan complex, biocompatibility, biodegradability, demineralization, deproteinization.

The excretion of radionuclides, toxic substances, pathogenic microorganisms from the human body contributes to healthy well-being and increasing lifespan. In recent years, special attention has been paid to the biopolymer chitin and its derivatives. Due to unique properties such as biocompatibility, biodegradability, nontoxicity, they have been applied in different fields: medicine, ecology, food industry and agriculture. The sources of chitin and its derivatives are the shell of commercial crustaceans, the squid's gladius, the cuttlebone of cuttlefish, the silkworm pupa, the cockroaches, the biomass of microorganisms, diatoms, and bee-pods. In the Republic of Belarus, fungi, insect scum, earthworms can serve to isolate chitin on the production scale.

One of the sources of chitin-glucan complex can be the waste products of microbiological industry, in particular, *Aspergillus niger* L-4 biomass, a by-product of citric acid production. According to various sources, the cell wall of *Aspergillus niger* L-4 biomass may contain up to 30% of chitin, strongly bound to β -glucan and melanin in the chitin-glucan complex.

The presence of β -glucan changes the properties of this biopolymer compared to native chitin. Antitumoral and wound-healing properties, ability to treat bacterial and viral diseases, ability to adsorb carcinogens, heavy and radioactive metals, ability to increase

storage period of food products are the valuable properties for application of chitin-glucan complex as an ingredient for therapeutic and prophylactic nutrition.

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Thus, the isolation of the chitin-glucan complex from the raw mycelium of the fungus *Aspergillus niger* requires low costs and at the same time solves a number of problems associated with the processing of the by-product. A very urgent task for the Republic of Belarus is to develop a technology for isolating the chitin-glucan complex from domestic raw materials, namely from the by-product of citric acid production.

Chitin was first isolated by A. Braconnot in 1811 from the cell walls of mushrooms and was named "fungine". In 1823, "fungine" was renamed into "chitin" by A. Odier. Only in 1931 G. Rammelberg identified "chitin" and "fungine" and gave these substances the common name "chitin". Research of possible applications of chitin began after the synthesis of chitosan in 1859 by C. Rouget [1].

The variety of practical applications of chitin and its derivatives is illustrated by high bioactivity and de-

gree of polymerization and acetylation. Chitin exhibits high reactivity in swelled state and this state can be used to synthesise its derivatives.

Chitosan is an aminopolysaccharide, produced by deacetylation of chitin. The amount of acetyl groups can be described by the degree of deacetylation. Scientists still argue about the terms “chitin” and “chitosan” [1]. One of the important properties of chitin is polymorphism. Chitin can occur as three allomorphs, namely the α -, β - and γ -forms. According to A. Komi and R. Hamblin, the allomorphs differ in the orientation of the micro-fibrils.

It should be noted that at present chitin, which is isolated from the commercial crustaceans, has been studied to the greatest extent; because of this chitin is the most suitable material for synthesis of chitosan.

Chitin-glucan complex is a structural component of the fungal cell wall. Different species of fungi are known to have different structural compositions of chitin and β -glucan making up the chitin-glucan complex in its cell walls. Due to the existence of β -glucan and melanin, chitin-glucan complex has useful properties. The most important of them are the sorption ability towards carcinogenic agents and radioactive substances within gastro-intestinal tract [2].

An important property of chitin is its biocompatibility with human tissues, that allows to use it in medicine. Biodegradability and ability to stimulate regenerative processes in wound healing increase the possibility of chitin application in medicine. The author [3] notes that chitin has no allergic effect and is non-toxic. Moreover, an important advantage of chitin is its ability to dissolve in the human body under the influence of lysozyme, that allows its use as a surgical suture material for intracavitary operations.

Chitin and its derivatives demonstrate antitumoral and immunostimulatory properties, which allow them to be used for the production of aseptogenic surgical threads, contact lenses and skin substitutes [4].

The authors [3] have found an explanation for the ability of chitin to reduce the growth of pathogenic microorganisms through the biopolymer's property of sticking microbial cells together and facilitate the penetration of their cells. The author [3] has noted that chitin's ability to produce infinitesimal quantities of hydrogen peroxide contributes to wound healing.

However, it should be noted that the mechanism of action of chitin in human blood is not fully understood. The authors [3] have presented the summary of results of the interaction of chitosan with proteins and nucleic acids, of the antiviral and antitumoral properties of chitosan derivatives, of creation of micro- and nanoparticles of different structures, of the chitosan-containing preparations, bioresorbable surgical suture materials.

The authors [2] have considered the possibility of using chitosan in biotechnology and medicine due to such properties of chitosan as biocompatibility and biodegradability by using chitosan as a covering for wound treatment, which allows to avoid additional disinfection of the wound surface.

Hypocholesteric activity of chitosan was demonstrated in pre-clinical tests. It has been shown that the

addition of chitosan to the diet reduces levels of plasma cholesterol. Research has shown that the use of chitosan as a dietary supplement controls adiposity and can lower cholesterol levels in the blood serum, but the authors have made the important conclusion that chitosan-based supplements cannot be recommended for people with an allergy to crustaceans [5].

The amino groups in macromolecules of chitosan make it more active and reactive. Due to ability of chitosan to dissolve in dilute solutions of organic and mineral acids to form colourless viscous solutions, chitosan is used in food industry as a thickening agent, jelly-forming agent and complexing agent. This fact is analyzed in the process of protein extraction from the flushing water in the ground meat industry.

Chitosan can be used as a stabilizer, in the creation of edible packaging, for the clarification of juices, beer and wine. Low-molecular weight chitosan is used as a flocculant and clarifier for beer and wine, and high-molecular weight chitosan is used as a film forming agent for food packaging. The authors [6] recommend using of chitosan-based plastic food wrap for food packaging. As a result of studies, it was found that the use of chitosan-based plastic food wrap even with low concentrations of chitosan can inhibit the growth of pathogenic microorganisms and protect the product from the ingress of moisture.

Researchers from the US Department of Agriculture Research Center in New Orleans suggest the use of chitosan as a preservative to preserve the fresh taste of beef, because carboxymethyl chitosan is consistent with muscle proteins in meat and can bind iron atoms, preventing their reaction with oxygen [7].

As a result of experiments [8] it was found that chitin and chitosan are not inferior in their sorption capacity to other adsorbents used in wine industry, so there is a possibility of using chitin and chitosan for adsorption of phenolic compounds in white grape wine production.

In the cosmetic industry, chitosan is used as a gelation agent, film forming substance and anti-inflammatory agent. Chitosan-based shampoos give hair elasticity, help relieve static electricity due to ionic adsorption, and can be used for skin disorders. The antibacterial and hypoallergenic properties of chitosan allow the develop creams for problematic skin, and the gel-forming properties of chitosan can be used in the production of gels and mousse for hair styling.

The disinfecting properties of chitosan allow it to be used to protect fruits and vegetables from infecting agent. The methods of using chitosan for post-harvesting treatment of apples, oranges, strawberries, peaches, cucumbers in order to prevent their infection with pathogens of various kinds of rots are proposed.

The preparations based on chitin-glucan complex have been developed for pre-sowing treatment of seeds, increasing the yield and resistance of crops to diseases.

Thus, according to literature, chitin and its derivatives are unique natural biopolymers with many useful properties: biocompatibility, biodegradability, nontoxicity and bactericidal activity. These properties provide an opportunity to apply these biopolymers in all fields. But although a lot of research have been done, there are

still a lot of unresolved issues. One of the main problems is the development of scientific-methodological bases for analytical control of chitin, chitosan, its derivatives as well as products containing these biopolymers.

Currently, there are no technical requirements for raw materials for isolation of chitin and for quality characteristics of chitin in order to use it in a specific field of industry or in medicine. Moreover, the raw material base for chitin and its derivatives production is insufficiently studied, the problem of chitin and its derivatives production by ecologically clean wasteless technologies is acute, and the issue of normative and authorization documentation for products and substances containing chitin, chitosan, their modifications are also important.

The results of research of the morphological structure, chemical composition and X-ray diffraction analysis of the chitin-glucan complex obtained from a by-product of the citric acid production of *Aspergillus niger* L-4 biomass, as well as research of deproteinization and demineralization parameters of chitin-glucan complex extraction from it with the purpose of its further application in food industry and ecology have been described in [9].

According to the current epidemiological situation, it is also reasonable to extract chitosan or its modifications in order to investigate the possibility of using it as a medicine to cure the consequences of coronavirus infection.

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